

A PROPOSAL FOR IN-SERVICE CONTINUOUS TRAINING HAVING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION AS THE THEME

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7811293

Edelvira Silva da Silva

Professor of Specialized Educational Service at the Municipal network of Pelotas/RS. Master in Education from the Federal University of Pampa – Jaguarão campus.

Alessandro Carvalho Bica

Associate Professor I at the Federal University of Pampa. PhD in Education from the University of Vale do Rio dos Sinos.

ABSTRACT

This text presents reflections emerging from activities carried out during the development of the action-research entitled “A proposal for continuing in-service training with Inclusive Education as its theme”. It also brings the results of the training implemented based on research data that was developed throughout the Professional Master's in Education course, attended at the Federal University of Pampa - Jaguarão campus. The main objective of the study was to carry out continuing education with the teachers of a Municipal Elementary School, located in the city of Pelotas/RS. The specific objectives were: to sensitize teachers in the early years of elementary school to the relevance of work, especially with students with disabilities; reflect on the pedagogical practice in regular education from the perspective of an inclusive perspective; identify what needs to be done in everyday practice for effective inclusion; collectively plan intervention strategies in the teaching and learning process; monitor the investigative process through records; and evaluate everything that was done to get the results. Training was mainly focused on creating strategies aimed at the effective inclusion of special education students. The expectation was to promote a change of perspective in the teaching and learning process of the actors involved. The results, among other aspects, showed the importance of initiatives of this nature in the intervention of problems linked to the teaching and learning processes of these students, but, above all, to provide participants with new forms of continuing education based on their educational and social reality.

Keywords : Special education. Including education. Teacher training.

INTRODUCTION

This article presents the findings of an ongoing training experience developed with teachers from a municipal school in Pelotas. It deals with the description and critical and

reflective analysis of a training activity, with five online meetings held through the *Google Meet* platform .

Focused on the perception of the school's daily life, the practice had the purpose of promoting the constant and necessary reflection for the development of teaching with students who have some type of disability. Lück (2011, p. 89) states that the school routine

[...] reveals the dynamics of the school as a living organism marked by tensions between accommodation and transformation, conformism and resistance, individual interests and collective interests, conservation and innovation, common sense and theoretical propositions, spontaneity and organization, among other aspects. The daily management presupposes, therefore, the action in the sense of reducing the space of contradictions and promoting the articulations necessary to favor the overcoming of differences, without losing the richness of diversity.

The practice of the continuing education process was driven by the partnership and, mainly, by the discussion of what happens in the school routine, highlighting fundamental issues of initial and continuing training, which were highlighted by the research subjects by completing the questionnaire made available to the teachers. before starting the training process.

The conversation wheel as a methodological instrument opens space for the subjects involved in the training process to establish spaces for dialogue and interactions in the training context, expanding their perceptions about themselves and the other, establishing relationships of reciprocity and collaboration in a movement of understanding of the voice of the other. The conversation circles have their reference anchored in the “Culture Circles of Paulo Freire”, which provide moments of speech and listening. By listening to the other, we put ourselves in the place of subjects who learn from each other, exercising dialogue between practice and theory. For Freire (1983), “Culture Circles” are dialogue, it is the pronunciation of the world – that is, it is the process of reading the world, problematizing it, understanding it and transforming it.

DEVELOPMENT

This article brings an excerpt from a qualitative action-research, with the objective of investigating the problems and barriers that hinder the teaching and learning process of students with disabilities. Nowadays, action-research continues to be in great demand to solve collective problems and the learning of subjects and researchers involved in an action-research process . Action research follows a cycle that involves planning, implementation, description and evaluation of the change adopted to improve practice and permanent learning. In this sense, it

was seen as an opportunity to discuss the issues that caused the most tension and anguish in the daily life of the teachers involved in the study in the classroom , and, after recognizing them, directing effective actions with the aim of producing changes in practice. these professors and expand them to others.

Initially, a questionnaire was applied via the *Google Forms Platform* , which made it possible to learn a little more about the professional life and the opinion of the teachers about the continuing education carried out in service. The analysis of these data brought relevant information for the development of the research. The instrument was applied to 12 teachers, and a 100% response rate was obtained, which was considered an excellent beginning of the work, since it demonstrated the willingness and commitment of the school's teachers to participate in the study.

The teachers pointed out training proposals more linked to their practice, which does not need a solid and consistent theoretical training, so that they can, through training, understand their choices, their context and their actions on it.

The choices for training proposals centered on their practices tend to aim at training that is more directed towards their pedagogical work. It was up to the researcher to combine this practical knowledge with the essential theoretical knowledge when doing pedagogy in the classroom. Reflections and debates on what to do in the classroom constituted an important methodological tool for the success of the research.

VIRTUAL TALK WHEELS

The virtual conversation circles served as a meeting point so that each of the teachers could expose their ideas, exercise attentive listening to their peers' reports of experiences, reflect on their own pedagogical action and make decisions in the face of the situations that were reported in this formative space.

Reflection on practice, which, according to Freire (1983), is the confrontation between theory and action, also enables new perspectives for all subjects involved in the process, since “[...] there is only knowledge in invention, reinvention, the restless, impatient, permanent search that men do in the world, with the world and with others” (FREIRE, 1983, p. 33).

The meetings held constituted more than a mere coexistence or a meeting without deepening the theme, configuring themselves in a moment of deliberations of the proposals on inclusive education and, from the questions listed and discussed in the conversation circles, these proposals became to also be possibilities for qualified actions in the exercise of teaching

for the collective of school teachers. In the meetings, the concepts of curriculum adaptation, content and their differences in terms of design were discussed. We tried to make it clear that curriculum adaptation does not mean changing the activity for another that has no connection with what was proposed, but rather transforming it into a viable activity within the capabilities of the student with a disability. When proposing an activity that does not consider the difficulties and differences of students with disabilities, the curriculum becomes inadequate for the answers that the student needs to have. It is not a question of impoverishment or curricular trivialization, but rather, according to Carvalho (2010, p. 114) of “[...] finding ways to make curriculum content more flexible and provide everyone with relationships with knowledge”.

The author points out the need to adapt the curricular proposal, in which the Pedagogical Political Project goes beyond bureaucracy and will identify the school as inclusive or not, since it corresponds to the thinking of those who will be involved in it.

At that moment, there were our anxieties, doubts, pedagogical limitations, weaknesses and insecurities. And our strengthening was translated into supporting the reports of those who had already had some pedagogical experience with the target audience of inclusive education. In-service continuing education, in which that group of teachers was the protagonist, began to emerge as a new possibility of thinking together about the daily life of the school, the pedagogical practices and the next steps to be taken in the search for a school for all.

Training will not provide formulas for inclusion, nor solutions for difficulties encountered in the classroom. It will promote a change in the way of looking at the teaching and learning processes and, for that, the teacher must be open to questioning his way of teaching and facing the students' learning (MACHADO, 2009, p. 96).

Our experience in Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE) is based on the defense of an inclusive school that serves students in their entirety, through educational proposals that value their potential, minimizing their difficulties.

As Macedo (2005, p. 38) says,

[...] the challenges of teaching practice, in the terms in which it is defined today, assume that the teacher can leave the isolation and solitude of the classroom with their students and share collective ways of facing common issues.

Through the sharing of knowledge, each subject learns from the other, valuing and respecting different opinions, knowledge and pedagogical actions. Studies on inclusive education support the premise that teachers should not work alone, but rather in teams and in a collaborative and cooperative manner, so that good pedagogical practices are more successful.

In this context, training assumes a role that transcends teaching, which aims at mere scientific, pedagogical and didactic updating, and becomes the possibility of creating spaces for participation, reflection and training for people to learn and adapt in order to live with change. and uncertainty (IMBERNÓN, 2011, p. 15).

During these training meetings, the problems, difficulties and potentialities related to the students were collectively analyzed, until intervention strategies were found that could be implemented and evaluated in the classroom.

And this implies, through the rupture of traditions, inertia and imposed ideologies, training the teacher in change and for change through the development of group reflective capacities, and pave the way for a true shared professional autonomy, since the teaching profession must share knowledge with the context (IMBERNÓN, 2011, p. 15).

It was great to have shared a little of what I do and think with the teachers, who also do beautiful work and dream of a better school. We hope to have met the demands that the colleagues brought to the training, also considering the theoretical studies on inclusion. We need more research and connection with schools, and more teachers reflecting on and sharing their practices.

EVALUATION AND MONITORING OF THE WHEELS

Reflecting on the pedagogical action should be a constant practice in the exercise of the teaching profession, since every school year that begins we are faced with the most different situations in the classroom, in addition to a huge diversity of students. This takes the teacher out of his comfort zone and makes him look for other ways of teaching that benefit the students.

During the training process, we used the field diary as a methodology for reflection on training. The field diary allowed the researcher to exercise reflective writing, which helped a lot in the organization of this proposal, since this writing gave concreteness to the thought, identifying and correcting possible errors during the process. Through the reflection of this writing, the meetings were planned.

In the five meetings, an attempt was made to problematize the situations experienced by the teachers. Rethinking the practice led the teachers and the researcher to think collectively about the inclusion of all children in our planning and in our pedagogical work.

Pursuing teaching and learning for all takes time and effort. It demands restlessness, freedom of thought and decision-making in the face of situations that arise on a daily basis. I

proposed the following reflections on these perceptions, which are written in the field diary: will what was discussed about the Adapted Curriculum, Content Flexibilization and the Assessment Process during the five virtual meetings be reflected in the daily practices of the research subjects? Will in-service continuing education become a practice at school, since the possibility for teachers to talk and debate virtually has become a reality?

I am not here disregarding the importance of face-to-face training meetings, which are of great importance for providing us with physical contact and approximation with our colleagues; of being able to make a more eye-to-eye observation, paying attention to the expressions of each one during the discussions. This virtual format allowed the teachers to access the platform directly from their homes, or from another place where they were at the time of the meeting, with no need to travel from wherever they were to participate in the training. This displacement is, without a doubt, one of the barriers that, in most cases, makes it difficult to organize face-to-face meetings like these in schools. This training experience in the virtual format can be better used in pedagogical meetings, in meetings between AEE teachers and teachers who work in regular classes that assist students with disabilities, in addition to other types of situations.

The final evaluation of the research took place through a questionnaire, which contained five questions to be answered by the teachers about what was discussed during the five meetings of continuing education in service. One of the questions asked whether what had been proposed for the meetings had met the expectations of the teachers.

Teacher P3 answered the following: “Yes, they went even further. I thought it was great to have the opportunity to talk about each case, very specific”. In the same sense, the comment of teacher P11 added: “Yes, it was a pleasant space for discussion and learning that went beyond the initial proposal”. Both testimonies refer to what was initially established by the research subjects, that is, the debate on the cases of our students with disabilities, more specifically, and the sharing of our pedagogical experiences devoid of any criticism or prejudice in relation to what was reported by them.

The teachers were also asked if there was anything that should be adjusted or maintained from everything that had been talked about and discussed. In this sense, the teachers recorded the following: “I believe that the more practical examples, the better we can take advantage of. Theory is important, yes, but practice, the exchange of experiences is more objective” (P3). Teacher P12, on the other hand, pointed out the following: “Everything is growth. But a few minutes of exchanging experiences is more interesting than a lot of time reading slides, which becomes tiring”.

In the ideas expressed by the teachers above, practice, that is, “getting your hands dirty”, seems to have had greater relevance at that time. As a research professor, I understand that theory and practice must always go hand in hand, one contributing to the other. In the words of Macedo (2005, p. 39),

[...] I therefore defend a relationship of cooperation or reciprocity between reflection and practice, one feeding or complementing the other, in an irreducible, complementary and inseparable way. In concrete terms, this shift in emphasis suggests two questions: how to reflect on action already taken or to be taken? How to practice reflection?

The teachers also opined about the themes that were addressed during training, pointing out those that could most influence their pedagogical actions with students in the future. Teacher P4 stated that “[...] the AEE itself brings suggestions for activities and approaches aimed at including the student as a learner for the development of their potential and autonomy”.

It is believed that the reference made to Specialized Educational Service reflects the importance of this service in the school environment for students and teachers of regular education. It is necessary to create spaces for dialogue between the classroom teacher and the SEA teacher, in order to share information and think about effective actions for their students - such as the study of case, for example – with the purpose of developing them in their entirety and including them in their pedagogical proposals based on a more reflective action on the teachers' pedagogical practice.

Another issue addressed was the proposal for in-service training and the redirection of work with students with disabilities. The teachers said, in general, that the proposal was relevant and that it will help them in the preparation of their future plans for their students. As pointed out in her questionnaire, teacher P4 emphasized that

It was very important to carry out this reflection and discussion with colleagues for a truly inclusive school practice, where the management team, pedagogical coordination, AEE and common class teachers walk in the same direction. Certainly the materials studied and developed were very important.

Teacher P9, in turn, said: “I think it will always contribute to improving our inclusive perspective and improving our practice. It is good to exchange experiences, practices and knowledge”. Teacher P8 considered that the training proposal brought “a different look at the difficulties”, as well as teacher P3, who identified in training “[...] important things,

starting with the way of observing the student, of seeing what the real needs of that student to better adapt the pedagogical proposal”.

I believe that I managed to sensitize the teachers in order to sharpen their eyes on those who need and need only an opportunity to learn in the broadest sense of the word – that is, beyond historically constructed knowledge. Learning to live and coexist with the other with their similarities and, mainly, differences. Learning to love and respect yourself and, in the same way, love and respect those who think and feel the world differently from me. Learning to accept oneself as one is, understanding that what makes us human are our peculiarities, and that this is the “beauty” of learning. Nóvoa (2007, p. 29) points out that

Teacher training must be based on professional commitments, which are also social commitments. Educational work always implies an ethical horizon. In the first place, a teacher cannot resign himself to the fatalism of school failure. The acquisition of a pedagogical repertoire serves precisely to solve the most problematic cases. Secondly, a teacher cannot renounce the mission that society has entrusted to him. It is the most vulnerable who need more and better schools. Education for all only makes sense if it translates into learning for all. Thirdly, a teacher must respect different communities and cultures, without forgetting, however, that his purpose is to help children go beyond the boundaries that, so often, have been traced to them as a destiny by birth, by the family or by society. .

Quality teaching with meaning for students is indispensable, which includes cultural, social and political aspects, among others, and which aims at the full development of these individuals. Therefore, it is necessary to adopt as a frequent practice the in-service continuing education meetings, which, certainly, should be more in-depth in their theoretical and critical-reflective aspect. The intention is to focus on the pedagogical actions of each teacher in the light of some theories that lead us to reflect critically and (re)signify our role as opinion makers - devoid of any kind of prejudice, resistance, fears , insecurities, among others.

CONSIDERATIONS

The literature consulted about teacher training and inclusive education together with action research made up a significant set that contributed to reflect more intensely on the pedagogical work of the teachers involved in the research, as well as the rethinking of actions to qualify students' learning. students, especially those with disabilities. Our objective was to think of a proposal for pedagogical work within an inclusive education perspective, in which

ideas about learning and teaching were revised, considering the trajectory of each student and the universe of knowledge possibilities to be developed.

It was understood that the sharing of ideas, experiences and emotions enrich the work and manifest a feeling of authorship for everything that is built and that belongs to the school space.

It was also observed, through the evaluations of the teachers, that the objectives that were thought for the research-action, in the majority, were reached. However, it is believed that the critical reflection on the practice could have been better explored and deepened through the texts that were worked on and indicated as theoretical support. That is, to focus on our pedagogical work, analyzing it critically, based on a theory that helps us find ways and meaning for our craft, allowing us to talk about it without squeamishness.

I understand that the study carried out was not exhausted, because what was reported is just a cut of what studies in the area of Special Education represent from the perspective of Inclusive Education and Continuing Education. The experience of being a research professor was challenging, as it took me out of my comfort zone and routine, demanding a lot of involvement with research. I see that there is still a long way to go in the search for a school for all, perceived through the considerations made by the various authors that underlie this study.

This is a discussion that should be made by all of Brazilian society, not just by specialists or theorists who study inclusive education. It is extremely necessary that this agenda be discussed and defended by all in the search for a more generous, plural, democratic and socially just country.

REFERENCES

CARVALHO, Rosita Edler. **Inclusive School: the reorganization of the pedagogical work.** Porto Alegre: Mediation, 2010.

FREIRE, Paul. **Pedagogy of the Oppressed** . 18 ed. Rio de Janeiro: Paz e Terra, 1983.

IMBERNON, Francisco. **Teacher and Professional Training: training for change and uncertainty.** São Paulo: Cortez, 2011.

LUCK, Heloisa. **Management of the School's Organizational Culture and Climate** . 2nd ed. Petropolis: Voices, 2011.

MACEDO, Lino de. **Pedagogical Essays: How to Build a School for All?** Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2005.

MACHADO, Rosangela. **Special Education in Inclusive School: Policies, Paradigms and Practices.** 1st ed. São Paulo: Cortez, 2009.

NOVOA, Antonio. In search of lucidity and coherence – for a preface. In: VICTOR, Sonia Lopes; DRAGO, Rogério, CHICON, José Francisco, (orgs). **Inclusive Education for Children, Adolescents, Young People and Adults** : advances and challenges. Vitória: EDUFES, 2007.